

Solvation shells and radial distribution functions of transition metal complexes in aqueous solution: results from ab initio molecular dynamics

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We present the radial distribution functions and solvation shell results obtained for several metal cations and transition metal complexes in solution. All the systems under study are electrochemically active redox couples. The data was collected from ab initio molecular dynamics based on the PBE functional and PBE with Tkatchenko-Scheffler van der Waals corrections. The systems studied are $\text{Cr}^{+2/+3}$, $\text{V}^{+2/+3}$, $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{+2/+3}$, $\text{Sn}^{+2/+4}$, $\text{Cu}^{+1/+2}$, $\text{FcMeOH}^{0/+1}$ (ferrocene methanol), $\text{Fe}^{+2/+3}$ and $\text{Fc}^{0/+1}$ (ferrocene). An analysis of the free energy differences and estimated redox potentials for these couples will be published elsewhere.

We performed ab initio molecular dynamics (MD) of the following redox couples in solution: $\text{Cr}^{+2/+3}$, $\text{V}^{+2/+3}$, $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6^{+2/+3}$, $\text{Sn}^{+2/+4}$, $\text{Cu}^{+1/+2}$, $\text{FcMeOH}^{0/+1}$ (ferrocene methanol), $\text{Fe}^{+2/+3}$ and $\text{Fc}^{0/+1}$ (ferrocene). All the couples were studied in aqueous solution, except for ferrocene, which was solvated in acetonitrile. The redox systems were put in a cubic box of $12 \times 12 \times 12 \text{ \AA}^3$ under periodic boundary conditions ($14 \times 14 \times 14 \text{ \AA}^3$ for ferrocene). All the metal atoms were solvated with 57 water molecules, whereas $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6$, FcMeOH and Fc were solvated with 53 water, 46 water and 20 acetonitrile molecules, respectively. The different systems were preequilibrated using classical force fields with Gromacs [1]. After this, 35 ps of ab initio molecular dynamics (AIMD) followed, of which the last 20 ps are analyzed (V^{+2} was equilibrated for an extra 40 ps). The AIMD was carried out with the VASP code [2] and PAW potentials [3], with 300 eV as cutoff energy for plane waves. A Nosé-Hoover [4, 5] thermostat was used to maintain the temperature around 300 K. The integration time step was chosen as 0.5 fs to correctly resolve hydrogen vibrations. We tested the PBE functional [6] and PBE with Tkatchenko-Scheffler (PBE+TS) dispersion corrections [7]. The PBE+TS simulations were started using the PBE final geometries as starting point.

The radial distribution functions (RDFs) are averaged over the whole trajectory. They are given in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The numbers placed on the red curves indicate the integrated RDF up to that point, as a way to estimate the average number of nearest-neighbors up to that position. More precisely, the value is

$$N = 4\pi\rho \int_0^\infty dr r^2 g(r), \quad (1)$$

where $g(r)$ is the RDF and ρ is the atomic density of the species under study (number of atoms of that species divided by supercell volume).

The solvation shells are given in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 for

the metal cations (that is, all the systems except for $\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6$, FcMeOH and Fc) and are estimated from the number of oxygen atoms within bonding distance from the metal, from bond-creation and bond-annihilation criteria. A bonded O was established as an O which came to be within a 2.5 \AA radius from the metal and did not separate beyond 3 \AA . The corresponding cutoffs for O-H bonding were 1.1 \AA and 1.3 \AA . This allows to establish the number and nature of water molecules around a metal cation, as well as the overall probability (measured as portion of the dynamics) to find a particular solvation shell structure. For instance, for Cu^{+1} treated with the PBE+TS functional it was found that the solvation shell was made up of two water molecules 58% of the time, three water molecules 38% of the time, and one water molecule and one OH group during 5% of the time. Besides the figures, these numbers are summarized in Table I. The solvation shell analysis was carried out with the topology reconstruction feature implemented in the DoSPT code [8].

In the following, we briefly discuss the results for each of the couples.

Chromium +2/+3

$\text{Cr}^{+2/+3}$ shows a solvation structure to some degree dependent on the used functional. Cr^{+2} tends to bind between 4 and 5 water molecules which are never broken down to other groups. Cr^{+3} can bind either 6 whole water molecules or 5 water molecules and one OH group. The simulations predicted one of the bound oxygens in Cr^{+2} to lie slightly further away from the Cr atom than the others.

Vanadium +2/+3

$\text{V}^{+2/+3}$ was a particularly hard case for PBE and PBE+TS. The free energy simulations derived from

TABLE I. Solvation shells for different redox complexes and probability to find a particular configuration during the MD. Only probabilities larger than 1% are shown (values are rounded up to nearest 1%).

	PBE			PBE+TS		
	Most likely	2nd most likely	3rd most likely	Most likely	2nd most likely	3rd most likely
Cr ⁺²	(H ₂ O) ₅ [100%]	n/a	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₄ [51%]	(H ₂ O) ₅ [49%]	n/a
Cr ⁺³	(H ₂ O) ₅ OH ⁻¹ [83%]	(H ₂ O) ₆ [17%]	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₆ [61%]	(H ₂ O) ₅ OH ⁻¹ [39%]	n/a
V ⁺²	(H ₂ O) ₅ [100%]	n/a	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₆ [100%]	n/a	n/a
V ⁺³	(H ₂ O) ₃ (OH) ₂ ⁻² [93%]	(H ₂ O) ₄ OH ⁻¹ [7%]	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₃ (OH) ₂ ⁻² [97%]	(H ₂ O) ₂ (OH) ₃ ⁻³ [2%]	(H ₂ O) ₄ OH ⁻¹ [1%]
Sn ⁺²	(H ₂ O) ₃ OH ⁻¹ [48%]	(H ₂ O) ₂ OH ⁻¹ [37%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ [12%]	(H ₂ O) ₂ OH ⁻¹ [84%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ OH ⁻¹ [11%]	H ₂ O(OH) ₂ ⁻² [5%]
Sn ⁺⁴	(H ₂ O) ₂ (OH) ₃ ⁻³ [81%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ (OH) ₂ ⁻² [11%]	H ₂ O(OH) ₄ ⁻⁴ [8%]	(H ₂ O) ₂ (OH) ₃ ⁻³ [61%]	H ₂ O(OH) ₄ ⁻⁴ [39%]	n/a
Cu ⁺¹	(H ₂ O) ₃ [79%]	(H ₂ O) ₂ [21%]	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₂ [58%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ [38%]	H ₂ OOH ⁻¹ [5%]
Cu ⁺²	(H ₂ O) ₄ [81%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ OH ⁻¹ [19%]	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₄ [78%]	(H ₂ O) ₃ OH ⁻¹ [21%]	n/a
Fe ⁺²	(H ₂ O) ₅ [100%]	n/a	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₆ [87%]	(H ₂ O) ₅ [12%]	n/a
Fe ⁺³	(H ₂ O) ₆ [93%]	(H ₂ O) ₅ OH ⁻¹ [7%]	n/a	(H ₂ O) ₆ [87%]	(H ₂ O) ₅ OH ⁻¹ [13%]	n/a

these dynamics showed the poorest disagreement with experiment for V⁺² and PBE of all the cases studied. Both PBE and PBE+TS predict V⁺³ binding 3 water molecules and 2 OH groups. However, for V⁺² the two functionals disagree even qualitatively, where PBE binds exclusively 5 water molecules and PBE+TS binds 6 water molecules. The computed redox potentials showed almost 1 V better agreement between simulation and experiment for PBE+TS.

Ruthenium hexaamine +2/+3

Ru(NH₃)₆^{+2/+3} was an easy case, since Ru is always surrounded by 6 amino groups, with both functionals yielding very similar results.

Tin +2/+4

Sn^{+2/+4} in aqueous solution is the only complex we studied in this paper which does not contain a transition metal. Sn is a large atom in column IVB of the periodic table. Its electronic configuration is [Kr]4d¹⁰5s²5p². Therefore, it easily adopts the +2 and +4 oxidation states. Due to the large charge and relatively low coordination, in both states the Sn ion tends to break down the water molecules around itself. In particular the Sn⁺⁴ ion can bind up to 3 or 4 OH groups (PBE and PBE+TS results, respectively). This indicates that Sn⁺⁴ may not be stable in solution.

Copper +1/+2

Cu⁺¹ showed similar behavior with PBE and PBE+TS, almost always binding either 2 or 3 water molecules. Cu⁺² also behaves similarly with both functionals, always binding 4 water molecules, of which some of the time one lost a proton to become an OH group.

Ferrocene methanol 0/+1

Since Fc is hydrophobic the bonding situation in FcMeOH was very stable. The cyclopentadienyl rings slightly increased their distance from Fe in the +1 oxidation state.

Iron +2/+3

Unexpectedly, Fe showed deviations from the usually assumed tetrahedral solvation shell. Fe⁺² showed exclusively 5-fold coordination with PBE and predominant 6-fold coordination (and some 5-fold coordination) with PBE+TS. In this case the inclusion of dispersion corrections was important to retrieve the expected behavior. Fe⁺³ behave as expected with 6-fold coordination with both functionals (PBE+TS predicted a small probability of finding one of the oxygens as part of an OH group).

Ferrocene 0/+1 (in acetonitrile)

The Fc couple showed unremarkable behavior similar to FcMeOH.

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FIG. 1. Radial distribution functions (RDFs) for different redox couples in solution and different DFT functionals. The numbers placed on the red lines indicate the integral of the RDF up to that point (and hence the corresponding number of atoms), according to Eq. (1). Vertical axes are linear from 0 to 1 and logarithmic beyond 1.

FIG. 2. Radial distribution functions (RDFs) for different redox couples in solution and different DFT functionals. The numbers placed on the red lines indicate the integral of the RDF up to that point (and hence the corresponding number of atoms), according to Eq. (1). Vertical axes are linear from 0 to 1 and logarithmic beyond 1.

How to interpret these graphs (example Cu^{+1} PBE+TS):

FIG. 3. Solvation structure of some of the redox couples examined in this work.

FIG. 4. Solvation structure of some of the redox couples examined in this work. Guide to interpret the graphs is given in Fig. 3.